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1. Introduction

This deliverable report some examples of climate impacting soil biodiversity (structure or functioning) as well as illustrations of key soil organisms that can serve as indicator for effective climate mitigation practices in agricultural management. The report will cover both indicators sensitive to climate change and able to assess the effectivity of climate mitigation management practices.

2. Indicators sensitive to climate change

2.1 Review of effects of weather extremes on soil biota

Climate change not only involves a gradual increase in average global temperature in the longer term but also is about the increasing occurrence of various extreme weather events. Both aspects may affect soil biodiversity. This chapter deals with the effect of extreme weather events on soil fauna in the short term.

2.1.1. Introduction

Weather extremes, such as floods, droughts, and cold spells have shaped ecosystems and organisms for millennia (Grant et al., 2017). However, the Earth is currently experiencing an unprecedented period of anthropogenic disturbances, and climate models predict increased intensity and frequency of weather extremes (IPCC, 2014). By definition, extreme events exceed the norms of environmental conditions and therefore drive significant mortality, resulting in range shifts, local extinctions, and transitions to novel ecosystem states (Harris et al., 2018). While sporadic extreme events can promote biodiversity and increase population resilience (Coleman & Wernberg, 2020), the increasing frequency of extreme events over the last three decades (60% increase in Europe, EASAC, 2013), threatens ecological, social and economic stability. Due to climate change, the most significant changes are observed in the amount of precipitations and the duration of droughts, but air temperatures are also rising, and heat-wave events have become more frequent (Tabari, 2020). These events are not independent, as global warming intensifies the risk of floods and droughts (Asadieh & Krakauer, 2017) and freeze-thaw cycles in winter and early spring, which can be destructive to agriculture.

Although extreme weather events are fairly well investigated in plant community ecology, much less effort has been made in soil ecology to study this aspect of climate change. Further, despite the documented importance of soil organisms on ecosystem functioning (Bardgett & van der Putten, 2014), even less attention has been given to soil ecological responses. Here we present a focused review of soil fauna responses to major classes of weather extreme events affecting agroecosystems in Europe (Devot et al., 2023), including drought, heavy rainfalls and freeze-thaw cycles (Figure 1). Heat-waves, driven by rising global temperatures, rapidly dry out soils and are most harmful to soil when not accompanied by rainfalls or when leading to a reduction in snow cover over winter which leads to soil freezing. As the effects of heatwaves on soil fauna is intricately tied to soil moisture, disentangling the effects of soil warming and soil moisture is difficult. Heat-wave effects on soil biota are therefore presented either under drought or freeze-thaw cycles in this review. Fires are devastating extreme events, particularly in forest habitats, and their impact on soil ecosystems has been well documented elsewhere (Agbeshie et al., 2022; Certini et al., 2021). Many environmental factors interact and affect soil organisms, and disentangling the influence of these factors can be extremely challenging. While tackling the effect of multiple stressors is outside of the scope of this review, it is important to be aware that stressors often interact and potentially exacerbate the overall impact on soil communities (Rillig et al., 2019).

For each extreme weather event type, we qualitatively review the available literature for effects on four major soil fauna groups: microbes (bacteria and fungi), nematodes, collembolans and earthworms. These groups have been widely investigated and are often used as soil biotic indicators in soil health (Faber et al., 2022; Rutgers et al., 2008).

Figure 1. Spatial and temporal variation in extreme weather events, and their major expected impact on soil physical and chemical properties. Images from [EcoWatch](#), [Euractiv](#) and [Grain Central](#).

2.1.2. Extreme weather description

a. Drought

Drought is a prolonged period of abnormally low precipitation. Water content in the upper soil layers is usually reduced relatively quickly, but deeper soil layers (30-100 cm) may not be immediately affected (Buitink et al., 2020). The rate at which soil dries will depend on the type and amount of soil and vegetation cover. Lower soil water content increases soil hardness and shrinkage and reduces water films making movements for many soil organisms more difficult. Unlike floods, which can occur over the course of hours and quickly inundate areas, droughts manifest more slowly in the soil environment. As such, soil organisms may have the capacity to move to more favorable microhabitats or enter some state of metabolic inactivity in order to avoid desiccation.

b. Heavy rainfall

Heavy rainfall can result in waterlogging, which compacts the topsoil with water, disrupting aggregates, and filling up soil pores with water, limiting aeration. Increased moisture is associated with increased nutrient leaching and reduced oxygen diffusion in the soil (Freeman et al., 2004). The oxygen concentration in waterlogged soils is significantly reduced after 24h (Banach et al., 2009). The availability of micro- and macro-elements in poorly oxygenated soils can be two to four times lower. This means that soil organisms have higher energy expenditure and need to be phenotypically and/or genetically adapted to survive longer periods of waterlogging.

c. Freeze-thaw cycles

Freeze-thaw cycles are by far the least investigated extreme event investigated in this review (Figure 1-4), likely due to the difficulty to assess it in the field. Freeze-thaw cycles can cause soil to crack and heave, which can cause loss of soil structure and erosion. To survive under frost conditions soil biota basically have to be able to cope with limited availability of free water, i.e. coping with increasing salt concentrations that disrupt cell physiology and induce osmotic disturbance. Thawing often results in rapid nutrient release, especially nitrogen, as microbial communities become more active. However, this nutrient release can lead to leaching, particularly in soils that are still saturated after snowmelt or rain events whilst plant growth is still neglectable. The increasing frequency of freeze-thaw cycles might make it more difficult for soil biota to adapt and respond, as it requires energy to produce anti-

freezing proteins or other coping metabolites, and the regulation of the production and disassembly of such metabolites becomes increasingly difficult to attain.

2.1.3. Effects of extreme weather events on soil biota

2.1.3.1. Microbes

Drought

Recent meta-analyses indicate an overall negative response of microbial biomass and activity to drought in arable and grasslands ecosystems (Amarasinghe et al., 2024; Qu et al., 2023). Drought alters nutrient availability to microorganisms potentially leading to starvation (Berard et al., 2015). Both strength and duration of the drought affect soil microbial responses and recovery, with the resilience of microbial biomass and communities decreasing with increasing drought duration (Bérard et al., 2011). This variability in drought stress intensity and duration partially explains why approximately 50% of the entries showed no effect of drought on microbial biomass (Figure 2).

Drought generally has a stronger effect on bacteria than fungi, reducing bacterial biomass, activity (especially for bacteria involved in organic matter decomposition and nutrient cycling) and affecting community composition (Hueso et al., 2012; Manzoni et al., 2012; Shi & Thakur, 2023; Thakur et al., 2022). Indeed, we found more reports of negative effects of drought on bacteria than fungal biomass and richness (Figure 2). This difference in adaptation is linked to particular fungal traits, for example their hyphae making them less dependent on water driven transport processes than bacteria when diffusivity is low. Consequently, drought events may increase fungal dominance in the microbial community (Barnard et al., 2013; Zeglin et al., 2013), however our results do not indicate that fungal:bacteria ratio is positively affected by drought. While fungi are generally considered more tolerant to soil drying, fungal activity also decreases under drought as saprotrophic fungi face reduced moisture for organic matter decomposition. AMF fungi, which are crucial for helping plants absorb water and nutrients, have been shown to benefit crop plants particularly under dry conditions (Tang et al., 2024). Within the bacteria group, Gram-positive bacteria are thought to be better adapted to high water potential than Gram-negative bacteria, as they have thick and rigid cell walls, high osmoregulatory abilities and spore-forming ability (Thakur et al., 2022). Drought could therefore shift the ratio towards Gram-positive bacteria dominated communities as indicated by the literature review (Figure 1) (De Vries & Shade, 2013). Overall, reduced microbial activity can limit nutrient cycling, slowing the mineralization of nitrogen and phosphorus, thereby reducing natural soil fertility. Other microbially mediated soil functions (e.g. soil structure and disease suppression) may also be hampered, particularly when conditions persist.

Heavy rainfalls, floodings

Flooding effects on microbes have been less studied than drought (Figure 1), likely due to the difficulty in setting up such experiments in the field. Studies have shown that flooding leads to the inhibition of microbial growth and activity and a shift in the soil microbiome structure (Siebielec et al., 2020; Sorensen et al., 2013). Soil microbial communities may change from a diverse aerobic assemblage to a much less diverse and less active anaerobic community, which can further contribute to changes in soil chemistry (Freeman et al., 2004). Fungal biomass seems to be more negatively affected than bacteria by flooding and heavy rains, likely leading to a lower fungi:bacteria biomass ratio (Figure 1). Arbuscular mycorrhizal fungi (AMF) face challenges under waterlogged conditions, as their hyphal networks are more prone to damage in oxygen-poor environments (Figure 1). The effects of flooding seem to disappear after a soil recovery phase (Sánchez-Rodríguez et al., 2017). However, repeated flooding might have long-lasting effects on microbial communities and functions.

Freeze-thaw cycles

Bacterial activity decreases significantly during freezing, and many bacteria go dormant as spores. Thawing typically leads to a surge in microbial activity, as nutrients become more readily available (Borken & Matzner, 2009). However, if frost increases salt concentration, this will negatively affect microbes that are not adapted. Freeze-thaw cycles can damage fungal hyphae, especially those of AMF. Cold-tolerant fungal species can survive freezing but exhibit reduced activity during thaw periods.

2.1.3.2. Nematodes

Drought

Nematodes are soft-bodied fauna with limited dispersal abilities to water film around soil particles, therefore they are highly dependent on water availability for movement, feeding, and reproduction and vulnerable to water stress. Meta-analyses showed that soil moisture negatively affected nematode abundance and richness particularly in croplands (Blankinship et al., 2011b; Zhou et al., 2022). Despite the high occurrence of no effects with sometimes even positive effects of drought, likely due to variation in drought stress and soil conditions, we found 68% of studies reporting negative effects of drought on nematode abundances (Figure 3). All free-living nematodes in soil are likely negatively affected by drought, however, persister species, that reproduce more slowly, and predatory nematodes, that are higher up in the food chain, may be more vulnerable as their populations are slower to recover. Root-feeding and parasitic nematodes, that associate more with plants, which may provide soil microhabitats with enough moisture, tend to increase (Franco et al., 2019; Yan et al., 2018). We did not find strong differences between the nematodes feeding groups, except for less negative effects on fungal feeders (Figure 3), possibly due to their basal fungal resource being less negatively affected under drought conditions. We therefore expect only minor effect of drought on nematode community (Cesarz et al. 2017). This might be partially due to nematode resistance or lag effects. Several nematode species can produce dauerlarvae that can survive unfavorable conditions for several months or longer, and therefore nematode communities are likely to recover after the first rain. Most nematode indices did not show a clear response to drought, except for the maturity index, which seems to be more negatively affected by drought, indicating that the nematode community is becoming dominated by r-strategists, which thrive in disturbed habitats (Figure 3).

Heavy rainfall, floodings

Effect and recovery of nematodes after heavy rain and floods has been shown to strongly correlate with that of microbes (Franco et al., 2019; Sun et al., 2018), which can be expected for bacterivores and fungivores nematodes which respond rapidly to increases in available microbial resources (Thakur et al., 2014). In particular, extreme rainfall has been shown to lead to a decrease in fungivorous nematodes (Ankrom et al., 2022; Sun et al., 2018). We found that omnivore and plant parasitic nematodes responded more negatively to extreme rain events compared to other groups (Figure 3). Indeed, flooding of arable land is used as a preconditioning measure in bulb cultivation agriculture to reduce plant-parasitic nematodes (but is indiscriminately harmful to other soil organisms as well (Rahman Khan et al., 2023). Negative effects on omnivores might occur because this group is often combined with predators, and higher trophic levels have been shown to be more affected by environmental stress (Franco et al., 2019). The nematode maturity index (based on a colonizer/persister scale) was found to be negatively affected by extreme rain events in grasslands habitats (Figure 3) (Ankrom et al., 2022). While nematode communities often recover after the flood, continued conditions of waterlogging may affect soil animals through blocking soil aeration and the subsequent depletion of oxygenated soil water.

Freeze- thaw cycles (nematodes and mesofauna)

Some nematode species can survive freezing temperatures by entering an anhydrobiotic state, essentially “freezing” their metabolism until the soil thaws (dauerlarvae diapause). Similarly,

collembolans and mites can have various adaptations to survive freezing, such as producing antifreeze proteins or entering a state of diapause. However, rapid or repetitive freeze-thaw events can obstruct such physiological accommodation in nematodes and collembolans and hamper an adequate response to frost, effectively reducing their populations. Effects of freeze-thaw cycle on nematodes and mesofauna communities could not be assessed as we found very little studies investigating these organisms under freeze-thaw cycles in our review (Figure 2, 3).

2.1.3.3. Mesofauna

Drought

Extreme and prolonged water stress is expected to affect collembolans since the majority of species exhibit preferences for moist habitats (Potapov et al., 2020) and warming reduces their saprotrophic fungal diets (Sanders et al., 2024) and feeding activity (Birkhofer et al., 2021; Gavin-Centol et al., 2023). In line with this, we find predominantly negative effects of drought on collembola abundance and richness (Figure 4). However, drought has also been found to have no effect on collembola, likely due to variation in drought intensity and collembolans life-history traits. Many epedaphic collembolans (i.e. species living on the soil surface) can prevent water loss by upregulating their osmotic pressure even when the soil water potential reaches the level at which plants wilt, or by moving deeper in the soil (Holmstrup & Bayley, 2013). Interestingly, several studies indicate a community shift with increasing temperatures towards smaller species (Holmstrup et al., 2018; Krediet et al., 2023; Thakur et al., 2023), likely due to greater detrimental effects of warming on several large body sized collembola. However, the long-lasting effects of drought on collembola community composition and traits still need to be assessed. While less has been done on mites, perhaps due to their higher desiccation resistance as compared to other fauna groups. Studies in which drought was longer-lasting show that also mite communities can be severely affected by drought (Figure 4). Recovery of biodiversity after severe drought incidents can take several years due to the relatively slow reproduction of these animals compared to other microarthropods such as collembolans.

Heavy rainfall, floodings

Flooding and heavy rains consistently negatively affect soil mesofauna (Figure 4). Collembolans and mites benefit from moderate rainfall, but excessive precipitation can lead to population declines from drowning, lack of oxygen, and habitat disturbance. Many soil mesofauna species can recover fast after flooding by surviving flooded conditions in soil as eggs, or by re-colonizing and reproducing quickly after flooding. For example, collembolan species have evolved strategies to survive periods of inundation, such as a buoyant integument that allows for flotation, and numerous additional physiological, physical, and behavioral adaptations (Witteveen & Jooisse, 1988).

2.1.3.4. Earthworms

Drought

Water and heat stress have well documented negative effects on earthworms (Eggleton et al., 2009), as they require a moist microhabitat for movement, reproduction and feeding (Figure 5). Similarly to collembolans earthworms retreat to deeper soil layers, and some species can enter a state of aestivation (dormancy) to avoid desiccation. Such avoidance mechanisms will temporarily coincide with reduced soil functioning. Moreover, prolonged droughts can severely reduce earthworm populations due to desiccation (Plum & Filser, 2005), and the impact on soil health may last longer. Deep-burrowing (anecic) earthworms contribute to the essential ecosystem service of water regulation. Their deep, vertical burrows facilitate water flow as well as deeper plant rooting, the former supporting the prevention of flooding and waterlogging, the latter improving plant drought

tolerance. The presence of earthworms has been found to also reduce the effect of drought on plant biomass and to slow down the desiccation rate of soils (Hodson et al., 2023).

Heavy rainfall, floodings

While several earthworm species have resistant cocoons and can survive in aerated waterlogged conditions for considerable time (Plum, 2005; Plum & Filser, 2005; Zorn et al., 2005), earthworms are vulnerable to frequent waterlogging as it restricts their movement and oxygen intake (Figure 5) (Harvey et al., 2019; Ivask et al., 2012; Kiss et al., 2021; Zorn et al., 2005). Earthworms have various physiological adaptations to overcome the lack of oxygen under water, and several species including *Lumbricus rubellus* may survive up to several weeks in flooded soil (Plum, 2005; Zorn et al., 2008). Earthworm populations can recover and recolonize fast after a flooding event, however prolonged waterlogging will negatively affect recovery due to low oxygen content (Plum & Filser, 2005). Higher temperatures might exacerbate the effects of flooding, as prolonged floodings have been shown to be much more devastating in summertime than in winter (Faber et al., 2002; Plum & Filser, 2005). The loss of earthworms under prolonged flooding has also been associated to a loss of soil functionality in the short-term (Harvey et al., 2019; Ivask et al., 2012).

Freeze-thaw cycles

Despite very few studies assessing earthworms under freeze-thaw cycles (Figure 5), earthworms are highly vulnerable to freeze-thaw cycles, especially surface-dwelling species. Some species burrow deeper to escape freezing, but soil heaving can expose them to freezing temperatures, leading to significant mortality. Increasing frequencies of such cycles replacing a single winter period may introduce a risk for mismatches in osmoregulation and other frost adaptation mechanisms.

2.1.4. Conclusions and research outlook

In this report, we aimed to provide a qualitative overview of the effect of selected extreme weather events on soil fauna within crop and grassland habitats. While this review does not delve into specific mechanisms due to its qualitative nature, we highlight areas for future investigation, emphasizing the need for complementary quantitative approaches.

The investigation into the effect of weather extremes on soil fauna remains an essential yet underexplored field. While substantial strides have been made in understanding the effects of certain climate extremes such as droughts, we identified a significant gap in research related to other extremes, particularly floods and freeze-thaw cycles in crop and grassland habitats. Another limitation is due to the great variation in the intensity and duration of stress events in the published literature. Therefore, reported “no effects” can be misleading without a nuanced understanding of how stress severity, timing, and duration contribute to ecological outcomes. A more comprehensive analysis that encompasses these variables could reveal hidden thresholds beyond which soil communities may collapse or adapt. In addition, the role of soil type and climatic zone adds another layer of complexity. Soil fauna in different regions may display varied adaptations to extreme weather due to their evolutionary history. Integration of local soil and climate could help explain why many of the extreme events had no effect on soil biota.

In this report we focused on the effects of extreme weather conditions on soil organisms (in terms of abundance, species richness, and indices indicators broadly used). However, to fully understand the relevance for society of any changes in soil biodiversity as a result, it is imperative to further study soil functioning and the subsequent provision of ecosystem services as a result of transient or persisting changes in soil biodiversity. Real-world scenarios often involve combinations of stressors, such as drought followed by heavy rainfall or compounded effects from human activities like contamination and land management practices. Future research should delve into how plant diversity can mediate or

exacerbate the responses of soil fauna, as diverse plant systems may alter microclimatic conditions or resource availability for soil communities (Cesarz et al., 2017).

Investigating these combined effects could provide a more realistic understanding of how soil ecosystems are impacted by extreme events, and how climate change may affect soil biodiversity, and subsequently impact soil health. For example, studies on soil organic matter decomposition and build-up may highlight cascading effects of extreme weather events on carbon sequestration services. Ultimately, a culmination of extreme weather events impacting the provision of all biotic soil-based ecosystem services will depend on the post-event structural and functional recovery of soil communities. Given the limited number of scientific studies and their limited research time frames, and the lack of robust and consistent results, this is a significant knowledge gap that urgently needs to be addressed to evaluate soil health in terms of resiliency and to further support climate change impact assessment.

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2.2. Taxonomic and functional homogenization of earthworm assemblages over a 50-year period

In this section we propose new insights on providing indicators for monitoring soil biodiversity based on earthworms. To exemplify some of them, we use a dataset from the #Vers2022 project that has been used to assess 50-yr changes in earthworm assemblage in France (Gérard et al., in revision). This dataset is the result of a resampling campaign of Marcel Bouché's historical localities, which was carried out between 2019 and 2023. For nearly 430 sites, it brings together assemblage data collected in the 1960s and resampled in the 2020s, together with environmental metadata. We assessed whether taxonomic and functional diversity have decreased over the last 50 years, in terms of local (alpha) and regional (gamma) richness and dissimilarity of composition between sites (beta). More specifically, we focused on species and assessed whether there were "winners" and "losers" species of the current global changes and whether winners and losers contribute more than stable species to changes in temporal assemblages.

2.2.1. Introduction

How species are affected by global change is pivotal for conservation. McKinney and Lockwood (1999) defined "loser" as species that decline due to human activities and "winner" as species that expand, taking advantage of these ecosystemic changes. These definitions can be applied to populations and be based on both changes in abundance or occupancy in a given area, which can vary in size (Dornelas et al., 2014). The general trends observed are that a small number of winners are replacing many losers (McKinney and Lockwood, 1999). Interestingly, winners can be native or non native (Tabarelli et al., 2012), which seems to be mostly linked to their dispersal abilities (Filgueiras et al., 2021), leading to biotic homogenization at multiple scales. Therefore, identifying which species are winners and losers is one of the main objectives of conservation, and is strongly needed for targeted conservation efforts. Lists of threatened species, like the IUCN Red List of Threatened Species (Bland et al., 2017), are perhaps the most common and easily accessible way of identifying losers. They provide a categorization of the level of threat they face. However, while vertebrates are well assessed, a huge proportion of overall species are under-represented, especially invertebrates (Eisenhauer et al., 2019; Mammola et al., 2020). They also focus on extreme losers, as many species show declining trends but are not considered endangered (McKinney and Lockwood, 1999), neglecting winners and low-intensity losers. Another more reliable way of addressing winners and losers rests on estimating the direction of population or species trends over time (Wretenberg et al., 2006). The higher the slope, the more a given species is "winning" or "losing". It thus requires time-series, which are often lacking for undersampled taxa like soil invertebrates. Resurveys of historical data can be a good strategy to provide insights into biodiversity change (Hédl et al., 2017; Kapfer et al., 2017). Prach and Kopecký (2018) proposed an estimation of winners and losers with multilevel pattern analyzes initially developed by de Cáceres and Legendre (2009) to identify indicator species.

Currently, whether earthworm species are winners or losers is poorly known. To date, only 6.5% of earthworm species are assessed by the IUCN Red List (352 out of a total of 5418 earthworm species according to (Brown et al., 2023; Misirlioğlu et al., 2023)), and 54% of them are categorized as "Data Deficient" (190 out of 352). Germany recently paved the way with a red list of all German species (Gruttke et al., 2016). Even if the use of a red list is not necessarily the best way to assess winners and losers, it makes assessed species more known to citizens, which contributes a lot to species recognition and protection (Mammola et al., 2020), such as the giant Gippsland earthworm (*Megascolides australis* McCoy, 1878), popularized by David Attenborough, which is one of the first assessed earthworms on the IUCN Red List. Pérès et al. (2011) gave a vulnerability index for some species using vulnerability traits. Mathieu and Davies (2014) showed that northern France was recolonized after the last glaciation by a reduced number of species that we propose could be called winners of the glaciation ending. The winner and loser concept can also be extended to functional traits, as Gambi et al. (2016)

proposed for polychetes. It could be applied to earthworms: for example, heavy max weight is predicted to benefit from future climate in earthworms (Fourcade and Vercauteren, 2022), making it a “winner trait”. Ongoing collections of functional traits and earthworm resampling data (Ganault et al., 2024) are encouraging for winner and loser assessments.

This list of candidate indices is non-exhaustive, but can be used with ease in earthworm research, especially in the era of rising earthworm data, and could help prioritize soil biodiversity conservation planning.

Conventional approaches to measuring changes in diversity based on assemblage structure, such as alpha diversity, are of limited use in conservation because they do not take species identity into account (Magurran et al., 2019). Temporal beta diversity, which measures temporal changes in assemblage composition, takes into account the loss, gain and changes in relative abundance of species (Shimadzu et al., 2015). The intensification of changes in assemblage composition is now considered to be one of the most important effects of global change (Dornelas et al., 2023). Although the implications of these changes for ecosystem functioning are unclear (Magurran & Henderson, 2010), they can have major consequences depending on whether or not the loss of species is offset by the gain of species that perform the same functions (which seems to be the norm, Houlihan et al., 2007). So, in addition to identifying the identity of winners and losers, we also need to measure how they contribute to temporal changes in assemblages, and in particular to changes explained by the gain or loss of species.

2.2.2. Identity of winner and loser species

Most species (94 out of 115, or 83%) are classified as **stable**, meaning they do not exhibit a significant temporal trend. A significant temporal trend was observed for 21 out of 115 species (18%). Eleven species (9.6%) can be considered **winners** because they show a significant positive temporal trend: *Allolobophora s.s. chlorotica chlorotica* (Savigny, 1826), *Allolobophora s.s. icterica* (Savigny, 1826), *Aporrectodea s.s. longa* (Ude, 1885), *Aporrectodea s.l. rosea* (Savigny, 1826), *Aporrectodea s.s. rubicunda rubicunda* (Vedovini, 1969), *Aporrectodea s.s. voconca* (Bouché, 1972), *Dendrobaena attemsi* (Michaelson, 1902), *Dendrobaena octaedra* (Savigny, 1826), *Murchieona muldali* (Omodeo, 1956), *Octolasion lacteum* (Örley, 1885), and *Proselodrilus amplisetosus amplisetosus* (Bouché, 1972). Ten other species (8.7%) can be considered **losers** because they exhibit a significant negative temporal trend: *Aporrectodea s.s. ripicola* (Bouché, 1972), *Avelona ligra* (Bouché, 1969), *Bimastos rubidus* (Savigny, 1826), *Eiseniella tetraedra* (Savigny, 1826), *Helodrilus oculatus* (Hoffmeister, 1845), *Lumbricus bouchei* (Zicsi & Csuzdi, 1999), *Lumbricus festivus* (Savigny, 1826), the *Lumbricus "terrestris"* Linnaeus, 1758 complex, *Scherotheca monspessulensis idica* Bouché, 1972, and *Scherotheca savignyi* (Guerne & Horst, 1893).

Among the "stable" species, twelve were collected during the re-sampling but were absent from the initial inventory (10.4% of the total number of species): *Amyntas diffringens* (Baird, 1869), *Aporrectodea s.l. sineporis* (Omodeo, 1952), *Bimastos parvus* (Eisen, 1874), *Gatesona cortezi* (Qiu & Bouché, 1998), *Kritodrilus setusmonsanus* (Qiu & Bouché, 1998), *Murchieona minuscula* (Rosa, 1906), *Octodrilus hemiandrus* (Cognetti, 1901), *Scherotheca haymozi* (Zicsi, 1977), *Scherotheca minor minorissima* Qiu & Bouché, 1998, *Scherotheca monspessulensis monspessulensis* Bouché, 1972, *Scherotheca sanaryensis* (Tetry, 1942), *Zophoscolex atlanticus* (Bouché, 1969a). Ten other species present in the historical data were not found during re-sampling (8.7% of the total): *Boucheona tenebrae* (Marchán et al., 2023), *Cataladrilus catalaunensis* Bouché, 1972, *Coventina putricola putricola* (Bouché, 1972), *Dendrobaena platyura* (Fitzinger, 1833), *Ethnodrilus zajonci* Bouché, 1972, *Proselodrilus amplisetosus hexathecosus* Bouché, 1972, *Proselodrilus elusatus* Bouché, 1972, *Proselodrilus pyrenaicus abduhi* Qiu & Bouché, 1998, *Scherotheca dinoscolex* (Bouché, 1972), *Scherotheca mifuga* (Bouché, 1972).

Among the winner species (n=11), all experienced an increase in site occupancy, but five showed a decrease in relative abundance. All winner species are native to France, and three are endemic to the country, while the others are considered colonizing species. Of the species newly present during re-sampling (n=12), eight are native to France, one is exotic, and three have uncertain status. Seven are endemic to France, and two are considered colonizing species. Among the loser species (n=10), all experienced a decrease in site occupancy, but one species showed an increase in relative abundance. Nine are native to France, and one is exotic. Finally, four are endemic to France (and one to both France and Spain), while the others are considered colonizing species. Of the species not found during re-sampling (n=10), all are native to France, nine of which are endemic to France or the France-Iberian Peninsula complex, and none are considered colonizing species.

2.2.3. Contribution of species to Temporal Beta Diversity

The mean Temporal Beta Diversity Index (TBI) across all sites is 0.70 (Figure 2). The portion of TBI explained by species loss (TBI_{loss}) is 0.31, representing 45% of TBI, and is significantly lower than the portion explained by species gain (TBI_{gain}), which is 0.39, accounting for 55% of TBI.

Figure 2: Temporal Beta Diversity, decomposed in species gain (TBI_{gain}) and species loss (TBI_{loss}). *** : pvalue < 0.001 (Wilcoxon signed rank test).

Loser species predominantly contribute negatively to TBI, while winner species show more variable contributions (Figure 3). Among the species contributing most positively to TBI ($\Delta TBI > 0.005$) are *Octolasion cyaneum* (Savigny, 1826), *Aporrectodea s.s. trapezoides* (Dugès, 1828), *Aporrectodea s.s. nocturna* (Evans, 1946), the *Lu. "terrestris"* complex, *Mu. muldali*, and *Satchelius mammalis* (Savigny, 1826). Conversely, species contributing most negatively to TBI ($\Delta TBI < -0.005$) include *Aporrectodea s.s. caliginosa caliginosa* (Savigny, 1826) and *Al. chlorotica chlorotica*. Nine out of eleven winner species contribute negatively to TBI_{loss}, except *Mu. muldali* and *De. octaedra*. Moreover, eight out of eleven winner species contribute positively to TBI_{gain} (Figure 3). *De. octaedra* is the only winner contributing negatively to TBI_{gain} and positively to TBI_{loss}. All loser species contribute positively to TBI_{loss}, while eight out of ten loser species contribute negatively to TBI_{gain} (Figure 4).

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Figure 3: Changes in relative abundance of French earthworm species and their contribution to temporal beta diversity. On the left, the bars indicate changes in abundance (denoted as mean(T1-T2)) (positive = greater abundance today, negative = lower abundance today). On the right, the bars indicate each species' contribution to TBI (denoted as ΔTBI) (positive = the species contributes to increasing TBI, negative = the species contributes to decreasing TBI). The bars and species names (abbreviated) are color-coded based on the results of the paired t-test (Legendre, 2019): Blue = significant result with a positive trend (winner) ; Red = significant result with a negative trend (loser) ; Black = non-significant result (stable species, labeled "neutral" in the figure).

Figure 4: Contribution of species to the Temporal Beta Diversity explained by species gain (ΔTBI_{gain}) and loss (ΔTBI_{perte}). This figure displays the abbreviated names of species whose absolute contribution to ΔTBI_{gain} or ΔTBI_{perte} exceeds 0.002. The gray dashed lines represent $\Delta TBI_{perte} = 0$ and $\Delta TBI_{gain} = 0$. The gray dotted diagonal line represents $\Delta TBI = 0$. The black dotted arrow indicates increasing ΔTBI . Species names (abbreviated) are color-coded based on the results of the paired t-test (Legendre, 2019): Blue = significant result with a positive trend (winner) ; Red = significant result with a negative trend (loser) ; Black = non-significant result (stable species, labeled "neutral" in the figure).

Overall, species contributing significantly to TBI_{loss} or TBI_{gain} tend to fall into one of three categories: winners with a positive contribution to TBI_{gain} and a negative contribution to TBI_{loss} , losers with a negative contribution to TBI_{gain} and a positive contribution to TBI_{loss} , or stable species with positive contributions to both TBI_{gain} and TBI_{loss} (e.g., *Oc. cyaneum*, *Ap. trapezoides*, or *Sa. mammalis*). Notably, *Ap. caliginosa caliginosa* stands out with the most negative contributions to both TBI_{gain} and TBI_{loss} . Most species (94 out of 115) have an absolute contribution to TBI_{loss} and TBI_{gain} below 0.002.

2.2.4. Discussion

In this study, we highlighted an equivalent number of winners and losers. Moreover, the winners appear to show greater gains compared to the losses of the losers, with changes in abundance being more pronounced among the winners than the losers. These results contrast with studies that show a global replacement of many losers by a few winners (McKinney & Lockwood, 1999) and the global trend of population decline (WWF, 2024). However, our findings are based on relative abundance data. Conversely, they align with the work of Dornelas et al. (2019), which suggests a balance between winners and losers.

Notably, the winners are predominantly species considered peregrine, with a strong colonizing potential. These species are often invasive in other contexts, such as *Ap. rosea*, *De. octaedra*, or *Al. chlorotica chlorotica* (Mathieu et al., 2024), and some, like *Ap. rosea*, are experiencing range expansions (Shekhovtsov et al., 2020). These species also recolonized northern Europe after the last glaciation (Mathieu & Davies, 2014). Thus, the winners are primarily species capable of recolonizing ecological spaces vacated (by glaciations) or those already containing other species (as in recent global changes). It is also worth noting that several of these species are cryptic (e.g., *Al. rosea* (Shekhovtsov et al., 2020), *Al. chlorotica* (Dupont et al., 2011)), with only certain lineages potentially being winners. There are also endemic French species among the winners, such as *Ap. rubicunda rubicunda* and *Ap. voconca* (recently elevated to species status by Marchán et al. (2023c)), which is a positive signal for the maintenance of their populations, as endemic species are typically more at risk (Işik, 2011). *Pr. amplisetosus amplisetosus*, also an endemic species of the pre-Pyrenean region, has been introduced and is now well-established in Ireland (Melody & Schmidt, 2012), indicating either invasive potential or at least a colonizing ability.

Loser species, on the other hand, are twice as likely to be represented by endemic species compared to winners, with nearly half being endemic to France and one species endemic to France-Spain. Among the losers is the *Lu. "terrestris"* complex (*Lu. terrestris* + *Lu. herculeus* (Savigny, 1826)), which shows the most significant decline in abundance among losers. First described by Linnaeus in 1758, *Lu. terrestris* is likely the most well-known earthworm species in Europe and is frequently identified (albeit often mistakenly) on the iNaturalist platform (<https://www.inaturalist.org/>). This emblematic species is therefore in decline. However, behind this complex also lies *Lu. herculeus*, distinguishable from *Lu. terrestris* only through DNA analysis (James et al., 2010). The observed changes in abundance may thus concern *Lu. terrestris*, *Lu. herculeus*, or both, though the restricted distribution of *Lu. herculeus* (north of the Paris region) suggests a decline of *Lu. terrestris*. More generally, the genus *Lumbricus*, which includes several loser species but no winners, appears to be particularly sensitive to global changes.

Among newly detected species, which could be potential winners, two are exotic, and three have uncertain statuses, with their new presence in France identified through the #Vers2022 project. This may indicate a possible trend of colonization of France by non-native species. Additionally, seven species with very small endemic ranges were detected, likely due to their low detection probability, yet this finding is notable. For example, *Sc. minor minorissima*, *Sc. haymozi*, *Sc. sanaryensis*, *Kr. setusmonsanus*, and *Ga. cortezi* were previously known from a single locality, underscoring the remarkable naturalist value of this discovery. Furthermore, within the genus *Murchieona*, currently bi-specific, *Mu. muldali* is a winner, while *Mu. minuscula* was only detected during re-sampling, suggesting this genus may be a "winner" genus overall, though the very small size of its species could

explain their lower detection probability in qualitative sampling. Among species no longer detected, all are native to France, and 9 out of 10 are endemic to France or the France-Iberia complex. This contrasts with the newly detected species, which include several exotic or potentially exotic species. Additionally, *Et. zajonci* and *Pr. amplisetosus hexathecosus*, known only from their type localities (re-sampled during #Vers2022), have not been observed again in over 50 years, raising significant concerns about their population sustainability and possibly signaling extinction.

Comparisons with long- and short-term observations by Lehmitz et al. (2016) and predictions across Europe and France by Zeiss et al. (2023) reveal differences from our results. Zeiss et al. (2023) predict future distributions of earthworms in Europe under climate change, forecasting expansions for many species, some identified as winners (e.g., *Al. chlorotica*, *Ap. longa*, *De. attemsi*, *De. octaedra*), losers (*Bi. rubidus*), or stable (*Ap. caliginosa*, *Lu. castaneus* (Savigny, 1826), *Oc. cyaneum*) in our study. However, none of these species are predicted to expand in France; instead, many are projected to decline due to a general shift in species pools from the west to the northeast of Europe. Results from the red list of Lehmitz et al. (2016) also differ from ours, with a majority of species that are winners or losers in our country but that are stable in Germany in the long term, but *Lu. terrestris* is increasing and *Lu. rubellus* and *Oc. cyaneum* are declining. In the short term, similar to our results, *Al. chlorotica* is increasing, but *Al. icterica*, *Ap. longa*, *Lu. castaneus* and *Oc. tyrtaeum* are declining versus winner or stable in our results, and *Oc. cyaneum* is increasing versus stable in our results. The future predictions by Zeiss et al. (2023) for France are quite clearly different from ours. This probably reflects a great plasticity of certain species, which despite global changes manage to benefit from them. However, future projections are based on a context of future global changes, exponentially more intense, such as climate change (IPCC, 2022). We are probably observing the result of environmental changes significant enough for plastic species to benefit from them, but which could increase beyond a certain threshold fatal to French species. The differences observed with the German situation, which seems more stable, can be explained by a different climate, mainly continental for Germany versus oceanic and Mediterranean for France (Beck et al. 2023), the Mediterranean climate being more sensitive to climate change (MedECC, 2020). France also has the specificity of having an area that served as a historical refuge during the last glaciation in its entire southern half (Mathieu & Davies, 2014), with a richer but less generalist species pool. These differences encourage studying winner and loser patterns on a regional scale in France, to detect possible north-south differences that could explain French specificities.

Finally, we can question the limits of Legendre's (2019) method for identifying winners and losers. This statistical method only produces significant results for species whose numbers exceed a certain threshold. Thus, very rare species, which make up a large majority of French species, will appear as "stable", while they may experience different dynamics. This is partly why we have highlighted the newly present species and those absent during resampling.

2.2.5. Conclusions and research outlook

In this report, we highlighted notable changes in the composition of assemblages, multi-scale diversity, population dynamics. These results are significant and confirm the hypothesis of a biodiversity crisis. However, the framework of this study offered relatively stable conditions, a priori not conducive to revealing major transformations.

Indeed, these changes were highlighted on the basis of a resampling work. Given the level of precision of the coordinates of historical sites given by Bouché (1972), we had to follow the "semi-permanent" plot approach (Kapfer et al., 2017), which consists of resampling the sites as similar as possible to those described previously. To do this, we chose to resample only sites with an environment similar to that described by Bouché (1972), excluding those whose environmental conditions had changed to the point of no longer allowing a comparable environment to be found. Our work is therefore based on sites whose habitat has changed at least minimally. We do not know the history of habitat use between the two samplings for each of the sites, and it is possible that some of them have experienced

disturbances between the initial date and the date of resampling. In any case, the similarity of the environment between its initial sampling and its resampling should partly limit the disturbances and therefore the changes observed in the composition of earthworm assemblages.

Secondly, the sites initially sampled by Bouché consisted almost exclusively of “semi-natural” habitats, including forest habitats, meadows (mostly permanent), riparian sites (river banks), and shrub vegetation sites (dominated by moors and scrubland). These environments, although dynamic, are rather stable environments when compared to more anthropized, urban or agricultural environments. In agricultural landscapes, many practices can impact earthworm populations, such as the use of chemical inputs (de Lima e Silva & Pelosi, 2023), metal pollution (Yadav et al., 2023; Chatelain et al., 2024), or physical soil modification practices such as plowing (Pelosi et al., 2014). Thus, the environments studied in this report are among the least disturbed, and should also limit the temporal modifications that earthworms can undergo.

Thirdly, we focused on diversity in temperate climates in Western Europe. This climate and geographical area are recognized as being among the areas that are currently experiencing the least landscape transformation and biodiversity loss, although they have undergone significant transformations over the past centuries. Indeed, European forests are gaining in area and productivity (Kahle, 2008; Pretzsch et al., 2014), which can sometimes lead to a decrease in biodiversity, linked to the loss of rich open environments (Preiss et al., 1997; Blondel & Aronson, 1999). Tropical biomes are generally highlighted as the most sensitive to global changes (Newbold et al., 2020), and are recognized as reservoirs of biodiversity on a global scale (Trew & Maclean, 2021). However, this is also the case for Mediterranean biomes, present in our analysis. The Mediterranean environment is experiencing fairly significant disruptions compared to the rest of Europe, and is more sensitive to climate change (MedECC, 2020). While Europe, and the more specific case of metropolitan France, are not exempt from threats to their biodiversity, this area is currently experiencing fewer constraints than other areas of the world. Thus, despite the framework of this work, which is rather conducive to the stability of assemblages and species compared to other parts of the globe, other types of environment or other sampling plans, we show significant trends, with sometimes small but significant effect sizes. This does not necessarily represent a good sign for earthworms, because we can probably expect more significant changes in other conditions.

Describing how much diversity has changed, how assemblages are transformed and how species react to global changes is essential, and represents a basic step (Gonzalez et al., 2023). In this work, we work over a long period of time, a period during which humans have considerably modified terrestrial ecosystems and impacted living things (Ceballos et al., 2015). We hypothesized that over the duration of our study, there was a set of disturbances significant enough to impact earthworm diversity, despite conditions rather conducive to stability. We estimated that the potential changes observed in earthworms were attributable to these global changes. However, we do not link the observed changes to specific factors, which places our work in a detection rather than attribution stage (Gonzalez et al., 2023). Detection consists of showing that a measure of biodiversity has changed compared to a reference, while attribution consists of assessing the extent to which various factors, potentially causal, contribute to the observed biodiversity changes. Since global changes are a sum of complex phenomena, it is not always easy to carry out attribution, but it is a necessary objective of monitoring scheme, complementary to detection, which can potentially allow the implementation of policies. The continuation of this work could therefore naturally be in the attribution of the observed changes, in particular by studying the role of threats to soils (FAO et al., 2020).

The patterns of diversity change observed worldwide are highly dependent on the geographic area (Newbold et al., 2020; Neugarten et al., 2024). While soil and climate is one of the primary factors explaining diversity changes (Jaureguiberry et al., 2022), the biogeographic context is also important. In France, biogeographic history plays a major role in the distribution of earthworm diversity and traits (Mathieu & Davies, 2014; Si-Moussi, 2020; Fourcade & Vercauteren, 2022). Indeed, there is a North/South opposition, with the North of France locally rich in species and traits, but with regional

pools of low diversity, and sites that are fairly homogeneous between them, while the South has low local diversity, but with rich regional pools and sites that are rather dissimilar between. Indeed, the North of France was covered during the last glaciation by a permafrost, which would probably have eliminated earthworms from the soils, while the South of France would have played the role of a refuge zone for earthworm diversity. The melting of the permafrost would have subsequently led to the recolonization of these areas by the most colonizing species, explaining the regional differences in richness. In addition, the Mediterranean area is marked by a drier climate that is more prone to droughts, which can alter earthworm populations (Singh et al., 2019). Finally, the South of France is also characterized by more significant climate changes than the North (MedECC, 2020), and different landscape dynamics with a closure of landscapes (Chauchard et al., 2007) and increasing urbanization of its coastline (Baccaini & Sémécurbe, 2009). Thus, these phenomena make it possible to hypothesize different diversity changes between the North and the South, in particular because it is not the same dimensions of diversity that are likely to change. **We therefore recommend that the future selection of candidate indicators of global change integrates large-scale and local-scale biodiversity changes, while ensuring that the interpretation framework is as local as possible.**

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2.3 Modelling soil borne fungal pathogens of arable crops under climate change

Soil-borne fungal plant pathogens are seldom considered in studies on climate change and agriculture due both to the complexity of the soil system and to the incomplete knowledge of their response to environmental drivers. However, some of them have been shown to be sensitive to temperature and represent an option of interest for simulating changes in biodiversity and loss of soil health due to climate change. Here we report an example taken from the study published by Manici et al (2014), where the soil borne pathogen of wheat *Bipolaris sorokiniana* was shown to be a good indicator to develop a species-generic model and to simulate its response under climate change.

2.3.1. Introduction

The need to anticipate and respond to the effects of climate change on agriculture presents many challenges. The fundamental one is to understand how climate change will influence agricultural and natural ecosystems as well as their services (Millennium Ecosystem Assessment MEA 2005). The projections of future climate impacts on agriculture have mainly been based on the impact of changing meteorological conditions on crop physiology (Rao et al. 2011; Tao et al. 2006).

Most of the available studies aim at quantifying yield fluctuations due to different thermal conditions and CO₂ concentration values affecting plants (e.g. Porter and Semenov 2005; Challinor et al. 2010). One emerging aspect concerns the assessment of the future dynamics of pest and pathogens of plants, which are key determinants both of crop yield levels and of natural environments (Anderson et al. 2004; Loo 2009). Projections of the future impact of air-borne fungal pathogens on crops can be estimated based on meteorological variables (e.g. air temperature, vapour pressure deficit, leaf wetness duration) and can be considered based on their interaction with plant biophysical processes (e.g. leaf area evolution, biomass accumulation, host susceptibility; Coakley et al. 1999; Bregaglio et al. 2013). On the contrary, the great complexity of the soil system adds a layer of substantial complexity to the forecasting of the impact of soil-borne pathogens on plants (Gilligan 1983; Hersh et al. 2012). Furthermore, there is an evidence that their responses to different environmental conditions could be very heterogeneous, thus potentially increasing their harmfulness (Broders et al. 2009). This leads to considering soil-borne fungal pathogens as one component in the complexity of crop-climate environment interactions, which makes projecting the net outcome of climate change in agriculture difficult; for example, the last USDA report on climate change and agriculture in the USA (Walthall et al. 2012). Soil-borne fungal pathogens are the causal agents of root rot in herbaceous and fruit tree crops and represent the main biotic components of yield decline in intensively cultivated areas. Their specific impact on yield losses is not easy to evaluate, given the difficulties in distinguishing their role from one of the scarce soil fertility or abiotic stresses; moreover, soil-borne pathogens can reduce crop quality in both direct and indirect ways (Dixon and Tilston 2010; Schwartz 2012).

The epidemiology of soil-borne pathogens is affected by several biological and physiochemical factors (Bockus and Shroyer 1998). They can establish symbiotic relationships with plants, having an impact ranging in severity from decreased growth rates to plant death, depending on host susceptibility and/or on environmental conditions (Redman et al. 2001). Given their saprophytic behaviour, soil-borne pathogens can expand in soil on organic residues (Bockus and Shroyer 1998) and in most cases vegetative hyphae can directly penetrate plant cells. This permits exploration, via purecultures, of their response to variable pH, nutrients, water availability, chemical active principles and temperature. (El-Hissy and Abdel-Kader 1980; Marín et al. 1995; Pettitt et al. 1996; Kim et al. 2005).

Soil temperature is the main driving force of the development of soil-borne pathogens and consequently the key physiochemical factor of their ecology, as water availability is often non-limiting to their growth in the presence of crops. However, an accurate estimation of soil temperature requires an explicit and reliable simulation of soil water content, which markedly impacts on heat transfer in soils (Lakshmi et al. 2003; Donatelli et al. 2014). According to the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC 2007), forecasts for the twenty-first century indicate a generalized increase of air

temperature and an intensification of the frequency of extreme events. Such changes are likely to impact on soil temperature regimes, potentially causing an increase of biological pressure of soil-borne pathogens on crops; in addition, they might experience shifts in their target host range, thus increasing the number of crops affected by their damage.

The objective of this paper was to develop and apply a large-scale simulation system to estimate the response of soilborne pathogens to soil temperature variation under a climate change scenario, covering Europe and targeting short to midterm time horizons, which represent those which are of most interest to set adaptation strategies to climate change in agriculture.

2.3.2. Organisms suitable to act as indicators for climate change simulation

Among several soil-borne fungal pathogens selected according to different temperature requirements and to their known economic impact on crop yield, *B. sorokiniana* (imperfect stage of *Cochliobolus sativus*) was selected as fungal pathogen agent of the foot rot pathosystem of winter cereals, representative of fall crops. It causes common root rot on wheat and barley and is present worldwide in major cereal growing regions. Warm soil temperatures favour its growth, and attacks occur between 16 and 40 °C, with optimal soil temperatures ranging from 28 to 32 °C (Mathre 1997; Mehta 1998). The growth response of this fungus to a range of temperatures was obtained in lab, and modelling the organism response to the temperature limits was defined (figure 5).

Fig. 5 Observed and modelled normalized growth rates of the soil-borne pathogen tested, *B. sorokiniana*. Different symbols correspond to different cycles of growth rate assessments in growth chamber.

Simulations across the winter period (October–March) of the growth rate of the soil-borne pathogen showed an overall increase in the future scenarios compared to current conditions (Fig. 6), with the highest peaks of differences in the coldest agricultural areas of northern and eastern Europe (e.g. Scandinavian and Baltic countries).

Spatialized simulations in the 2000-2020 timeframe of *B. sorokinina* presented an overall increase of growth rate (>25 %) in Denmark, Scandinavian and Baltic countries and in some cold continental areas of eastern Europe. Conversely, simulations showed an alternating slightly decreasing and increasing growth rate in different areas of Mediterranean and central Europe (Fig. 6). The projections of fungal growth rate in soil for this pathogen showed a variable increase (+5÷+35 %) in Mediterranean countries, France and in some agricultural areas of Germany and southeastern Europe in 2030. Peaks of differences in the relative growth rate above 35% are expected in the UK. This pathogen is characterized by higher temperature requirements than other fungal pathogens (Manici et al., 2014). This might explain why its projections indicate a generalized higher growth rate in the continental areas of Mediterranean and central Europe, with a marked homogeneity in Scandinavian, eastern Europe and Baltic countries in 2030, where soil temperature estimates are the largest given by climate models.

Figure 6 - Map of the increase of *B. sorokiniana* in response to the T°C variations (IPCC projection) across Europe. Differences of modelled growth rates of *B. sorokiniana* in agricultural soils of Europe between the winter periods (October–March) of 2020 and 2030 versus current climatic conditions centred in 2000 are shown.

2.3.3. Discussion

In analysing changes of soil temperature caused by climate change, a key feature to be pointed out is that this variable is, on one hand, positively correlated to air temperature, but at the same time, also a function of soil water content; the higher the soil water content, the lower the soil temperature. Hence, soil temperature is also a function of crop water uptake and consequently of the crop cycle duration; the latter shortens when temperature increases to the optimum for plants. This implies that not always a simple and linear relationship between air temperature, as driving force from global climate models, and soil borne pathogens response can be observed. Further, air temperature may reach, sometimes frequently, values above the optimum for the growth of organisms, whereas soil acts as a buffer thus determining a markedly lower temperature increase in the top layer soil compared to air temperature. In other words, when considering short to medium-term time horizons, the range of fluctuation of soil temperature tends to be still either below or close to the optimum. Consequently, in most of the conditions evaluated, the growth rate of soil organisms is rarely projected to decrease, opposite as it does for the above-ground organisms where the decline is frequent at the highest temperatures.

The simulations across the winter period (October–March) of the fungal pathogen *B. sorokiniana* showed an overall increase in the future scenarios compared with current conditions. The spatialized simulations of the foot rot agents presented a peak of increase in the coldest areas of Europe; this could be mainly due to the consequent reduction of limiting thermal conditions during the early growth stages of winter cereals, from germination to tillering development stages (Zadoks et al. 1974). These findings suggest that each of these pathogens will increase the possibility of becoming alternately dominant or codominant in function of the weather conditions from the seeding to the advanced tillering stages. Furthermore, temperature directly impacts on their pattern of distribution (Cook 1980; Daamen et al. 1991; Pettitt et al. 1996) and attacks of *B. sorokiniana* on winter wheat have been correlated with lower plant vigour and reduced yield (Sturz and Bernier 1989; Smiley and Patterson 1996). Consequently, the potential biological pressure of foot rot disease as biotic component responsible for yield decline of winter cereals is estimated to increase. Such increase will not be linear from the baseline to 2030 but is estimated to be more marked moving from the 2020 to the 2030-time horizons.

The general trend of soil-borne pathogen response to future weather scenarios, as outlined by this study, clearly shows a marked increase of their potential relative growth rate in the colder areas of Europe, but with some differences which should be investigated with more detailed information on

the soils and exposure. This may cause an increased susceptibility of winter cereals to foot rot and consequently a reduced stability of grain production over the years in the coldest agricultural lands of northern and eastern Europe. Crop rotation is the principal means for controlling soil-borne pathogens both in conventional and integrated production systems (Glynne 1965; LaMondia et al. 2002; Juroszek and von Tiedemann 2011); biophysical models able to predict the impact on crops of soil-borne pathogens should be considered by the European Commission when planning agricultural policies and guidelines for adaptation strategies to climate change in agriculture. This appears of particular importance for strategies concerning Integrated Crop Production, as this modelling solution for soil-borne pathogens simulation could represent useful support when adopting European Commission directives in the national Integrated Production guidelines by the EU-27 member states (European Commission DG ENV 2002; Boller et al. 2004).

Although the approach adopted in this study does not include the simulation of actual yield levels and quality decline of the crops, it opens further perspectives for the application of biophysical models in predicting response to climate change for a large number of soil fungal pathogens, either of agricultural or forestry interest. The modelling solution can be further developed to match in greater detail the phenology of specific hosts with respect to their sensitivity to pathogens. This would allow more specific estimates of the potential damage in future scenarios, thus reproducing with increased accuracy the complex interactions of the specific pathosystems. Such modelling solutions could be easily imported into the BioMA platform (Donatelli et al. 2012a, b) allowing an easy rerun of the spatialized simulations with different pathogens, and by including other key aspects of the agricultural systems such as estimates of impact on crops. Also, the parameterization of soils could be specialized both as soil type and as soil slope and aspect (i.e. exposure orientation).

The simulation system described in this study is a step forward in the analysis of production systems where there is a lack of adaptation of crops, hence allowing a more integrated evaluation of system performance in the future.

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2.4 Nematodes under changing temperature and moisture regimes

That nematodes are affected by climate change factors are well-known (e.g. section 2.1, Zhou et al. 2022). Often the effect on nematodes is evaluated by studying abundances and richness. For nematodes, there is a range of indices that can be calculated that might be better indicators for the effect of climate change factors such as temperature and moisture on soil nematode communities. By using already existing data from European-wide temperature and soil moisture manipulations in grasslands (Ekschmitt et al. 1994), we provide here an example of the usability of different nematode variables in describing nematode responses to temperature and soil moisture changes. Based on nematode genus data (available in de Goede and Bongers 1998), several different nematode indices were calculated allowing the comparison between nematode indices and more commonly used population variables such as abundance and richness.

2.4.1 Introduction

Nematodes are microscopic worms living in the water filled pore spaces in soil. Their activity depends on several factors in the surrounding environment, e.g. temperature and moisture. Temperature affects the rate of egg hatching and the development time (Kakaire et al. 2012), which in turn may affect the population growth and the number of generations per year. The mobility of nematodes is reduced when soil moisture is low because they rely on the water film around soil particles for their movement. On the other hand, nematodes can survive low soil moisture levels for longer periods (Neher et al. 1999).

Nematodes are fulfilling a number of important roles in the soil food web. There are beneficial nematodes being bacterivores, fungivores, omnivores or predators. On the other hand, root-feeding nematodes can have negative impacts on plant growth, yield and quality of crops. In addition to the abundance of nematodes, different nematode indices can be calculated on the basis of their respective c-p (colonizer-persister) values (Bongers 1990). The c-p values range from 1 to 5, and nematodes at the lower end of the scale are considered enrichment opportunists and therefore indicate resource availability. They generally have a short life cycle, a high colonization ability and are tolerant to disturbances (i.e. r-strategists). Nematodes at the high end of the scale instead indicate system stability, food web complexity and connectance, and are characterized by a low reproduction rate, a long life cycle, a low colonization ability and sensitivity towards disturbances (i.e. K-strategists).

The maturity index (MI) is a measure of environmental disturbance based on the nematode species composition (Bongers 1990). Low values indicate a food web with mostly fast growing bacterivores and fungivores and high values indicate a more complex food web that is usually more resistant to disturbances. The channel index (CI) indicates the dominating decomposition pathway of organic matter based on the occurrence of bacterial and fungal feeding nematodes, where lower values (< 50) suggest decomposition dominance by bacteria (Ferris et al. 2001). The enrichment index (EI) indicates food availability and nutrient enrichment, the higher the value the greater food availability. The structure index (SI) takes into account the nematodes that require stable conditions and the higher the value the more complex soil food web (Ferris et al. 2001). The objective of this case study was to evaluate whether nematode indices are suitable indicators for changed temperature and moisture regimes.

2.4.2 Nematode variables responsive to changes in temperature and moisture

Soil nematode communities clearly respond to changes in soil temperature, which is also evident when using nematode indices (Fig. 7).

Fig. 7. Linear regressions between soil temperature and a range of different nematode variables.

Within the investigated temperature range (10-20°C), all nematode variables but the enrichment index increased indicating that these temperatures are still within the suitable range of nematodes. Although not shown here, the abundances of the different types of nematodes showed the same pattern as for the total abundance. The response of the

investigated nematode variables were overall quite similar with soil temperature explaining around 30% of the variation. However, the channel index and the enrichment index responded poorly to temperature changes.

The nematode communities also responded to soil moisture content (Fig. 8). The three sites included in this example differed in soil types, two of them having mineral soils and one having organic soil (Ekschmitt et al. 1994). Consequently, the soils had very different soil moisture content before the manipulations, thus providing a wide spread of soil moisture levels.

Fig. 8. Total nematode abundance related to soil moisture content.

As for soil temperature, the different nematode variables displayed similar patterns with the exception of the enrichment index. However, the decline with increasing soil moisture content was substantially steeper for total abundance than the other nematode variables.

2.4.3 Discussion

This report demonstrates that soil nematodes respond to more gradual long-term changes in soil temperature and soil moisture content, in addition to responding to extreme weather

events as presented in section 2.1. However, temperature and moisture relate to each other (Zhou et al. 2022) and their effects are therefore difficult to disentangle. Nevertheless, the objective of this report was to evaluate the performance of different nematode variables as indicators for the effect of climate change factors such as temperature and moisture on soil nematode communities.

Nematode indices have primarily been used in the agricultural context examining effects of e.g. tillage, crop rotation, cover crops and fertilization or in environmental assessment (Du Preez et al. 2022). The most obvious result of this evaluation is that the channel index (CI) and the enrichment index (EI) are not suitable as indicators of climate change impact on nematodes. Both of these indices are more closely related to organic matter decomposition and microbial communities in soil than the other indices. Although microbial communities also are affected by temperature and moisture, other factors such as soil pH (Kaiser et al. 2016) and vegetation (Guasconi et al. 2023) are main drivers.

Both the maturity index (MI) and the structure index (SI) responded to the temperature and soil moisture regimes. This is indicative of that nematodes differentiate in their responses, leading to changes in these indices. However, it seems that these two indices are better indicators for changes in temperature than for moisture. Previous studies have even found that MI indices are not sensitive to soil moisture (Neher et al. 1999).

This report indicates that nematode indices, especially MI and SI, are of value in assessing the response of soil nematodes to climate change. However, a more comprehensive evaluation of nematode indices as indicators for temperature and moisture regimes are needed to fully understand their potential.

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3. Indicators sensitive to mitigation management practices

Biological indicators of soil health provide critical insights into the effects of management practices on soil ecosystems. These indicators are particularly sensitive to mitigation practices aimed at reducing the environmental impact of agriculture, such as cover cropping, reduced tillage, organic amendments, and crop rotation. Understanding these indicators enables stakeholders to evaluate the effectiveness of these practices and guide future soil management strategies. Here we report a brief summary of the results obtained in MINOTAUR testing a set of biological indicators on nine selected Long Term Experiments (LTEs) located in different pedoclimatic areas across Europe (more details have been reported in D4.2).

3.1 Long Tem Experiments (LTEs) and experimental design

We have assessed a comprehensive list of bioindicators (both taxonomical and functional) and related soil functions on nine selected LTEs that have been running by consortium partner institutions for more than a decade and include a minimum of three randomized blocks. These selected LTEs encompass a large gradient of edapho-climatic conditions and are located across eight countries, namely Spain, France, Italy, Slovenia, Austria, Switzerland, The Netherlands, and Sweden.

All the experiments assessed the effects of minimizing soil disturbance by comparing standard tillage vs. reduced or no-tillage and/or implementing distinct fertilization approaches (mineral vs. organic amendments) under different pedoclimatic conditions (Table 1). At each LTE we assessed several biodiversity indicators, encompassing all soil biota groups (microbiota, micro-, meso-, macro-fauna).

Table 1. LTEs selected for Task 4.1 and their experimental design: Fertilization treatments include mineral (MN), organic (OG) and non-fertilized (NF). The type of organic fertilization is shown. Cultivation treatments include Standard or conventional tillage (ST), reduced tillage (RT) and no tillage or direct seeding (NT). The numbers indicate tillage depth.

LTE - Experimental site	Country	Partner	Fertilization			Cultivation		
			MN	OG	NF	ST	RT	NT
SOERE-PRO-EFELE-TS-MO	France	ACO	X	Cattle manure		22	8	
FAST	Switzerland	AGS	X	Cattle slurry		20	8	0
Hollabrunn	Austria	BOKU	X			20	8	0
Fagna	Italy	CREA	X			40	12	
La Canaleja	Spain	INIA	X	Poultry manure		25	20	0
Uppsala research station (Säby)	Sweden	SLU	X			23	11	0
Lanna research station	Sweden	SLU	X	Cattle manure	X	23		
TillComp (Ljubljana)	Slovenia	ULBF	X	Compost	X	25		0
BASIS	Netherlands	WUR	X			25	20	10

3.2 Variation of soil biological indicators

3.2.1. Microbiota

Soil microbiota biomass indicators included bacterial and fungal biomass measured through the use of Fatty Acid Methyl Esters (FAMES), which are compounds derived from the esterification of fatty acids with methanol. FAMES are used as biomarkers for the presence of specific microbial groups and to assess microbial community structure. Both bacterial and fungal biomass varied significantly across long-term experiments (LTE) and were sensitive to tillage practices Figure 9.

Figure 9. Variation on bacterial and fungal biomass across the studied LTEs

Soil microbiota functional indicators included the copy numbers of functional genes such as the *phoD* gene, which encodes for an alkaline phosphatase enzyme involved in phosphorus acquisition by microorganisms. This enzyme hydrolyzes phosphate esters, releasing inorganic phosphate (Pi) from organic compounds, essential for microbial growth and metabolism. The *gcd* gene, which encodes for glucose dehydrogenase, facilitates the oxidation of glucose to gluconolactone, playing a significant role in microbial carbon utilization and organic matter degradation. Furthermore, the *amoA_bac* gene encodes the alpha-subunit of ammonia monooxygenase, an enzyme crucial for ammonia oxidation in bacteria. This gene is used as a marker to study the diversity and abundance of ammonia-oxidizing bacteria (AOB) in soil. Lastly, the *nirS* gene encodes for nitrite reductase, an enzyme involved in the reduction of nitrite to nitric oxide during the denitrification pathway. This gene serves as a marker for denitrifying bacteria and is critical for understanding the processes of nitrogen removal and cycling in ecosystems.

Similar to the microbial biomass indicators, the abundances (copy numbers) of microbial functional genes varied significantly across the long-term experiments (LTEs), with all genes, except for *phoD*, showing variations related to tillage practices (although not in every LTE; see D4.2). The *gcd* gene, which encodes glucose dehydrogenase, uniquely varied in response to fertilization. This variability is attributed to changes in substrate availability and shifts in microbial community composition. Increased nutrient inputs enhance the availability of glucose as a carbon source, promoting the proliferation of glucose-utilizing bacteria and leading to higher expression of the *gcd* gene.

3.2.2. Microfauna

Microfauna biomass indicators were assessed to evaluate soil health and microbial interactions, focusing on total nematode abundance and their functional group composition (Ferris et al, 2001; Figure 8). Total nematode abundance is reported as the number of individuals per 100 grams of dry soil, while the abundance is further categorized by functional groups, including herbivores, fungivores, bacterivores, predators, and omnivores. This classification provides insights into the trophic dynamics and ecological roles of nematodes within the soil ecosystem.

The abundance of nematodes varied across long-term experiments (LTEs), with LTEs such as ACO (France) and AGS (Switzerland) exhibiting the highest abundances of 5,586 and 4,311 individuals per

100 grams of dry soil, respectively, while CREA (Italy) recorded the lowest abundance at 172. Notably, there was a striking difference between the two LTEs located in Sweden, with SLU1 showing 4,176 nematodes and SLU2 showing only 367. Standard tillage practices generally resulted in lower nematode abundances. Additionally, the proportions of bacterivores and predators varied with tillage; however, no differences related to fertilization were observed, except for the proportion of fungivores.

Figure 10 - Variation in total abundance of nematodes across LTEs and tillage treatments (ST – Standard tillage, RT – Reduced tillage, NT – No Tillage). LTE acronyms as in Table 1.

3.2.3. Mesofauna

Mesofauna biological indicators included the QBS-ar index (Parisi, 2001, 2005), which is a quantitative measure of soil biological quality based on the composition and abundance of soil arthropods that provides insights into soil health and ecosystem functioning (Table 5, Figure 10). This index is calculated by considering the presence of different functional groups of mesofauna, their ecological roles, and their response to environmental changes. A higher QBS-ar score indicates better soil quality, reflecting a more diverse and active soil community that contributes to essential soil processes such as nutrient cycling, organic matter decomposition, and soil structure maintenance.

In addition, we assessed the number of Eudaphic, Hemiedaphic, and Epigeic organisms, which represent different ecological groups of soil arthropods based on their habitat preferences and behavior (George et al, 2017). Eudaphic organisms are true soil-dwelling arthropods that reside exclusively in the soil or the deepest organic layers. They are highly adapted to life underground and are rarely found on the surface, with examples including certain mites and springtails. In contrast, Hemiedaphic arthropods inhabit both the soil and the surface, capable of moving between soil layers and the litter layer, exhibiting intermediate adaptations to both environments. Lastly, Epigeic organisms are surface-dwelling arthropods that primarily inhabit the litter layer on top of the soil and seldom burrow into deeper layers. These arthropods are adapted to life on the soil surface or in decaying organic matter.

All four indicators varied across LTEs, although the QBS-ar showed the strongest response and was the only indicator that also varied with tillage treatment. None responded to fertilization.

Figure 10. Variation in the QBS-ar index across LTEs. LTE acronyms as in Table 1. The QBS-ar (Soil Biological Quality - arthropods) index is used to assess soil biodiversity by quantifying the abundance and diversity of edaphic arthropods, with higher values indicating greater environmental quality and ecological stability.

3.2.4. Macrofauna

Macrofauna indicators were utilized to evaluate soil health and ecosystem functioning (Lagerlöf & Lagerlöf, 2002; Paoletti, 1999), focusing on various metrics such as total biomass ($\text{g}\cdot\text{m}^{-2}$), total abundance ($\text{individuals}\cdot\text{m}^{-2}$), species richness, and the Shannon index. Total biomass represents the overall weight of macrofauna per unit area, while total abundance indicates the number of individual organisms present in the same area. Species richness provides insight into the diversity of species present, and the Shannon index measures the evenness of species distribution within the community. Additionally, the abundance of specific ecological functional groups was assessed, including epigeic species (surface-dwelling organisms), anecic species (deep burrowers), epianecic species (organisms that inhabit both surface and deeper soil layers), and endogeic species (those primarily living within the soil; Lavelle and Spain: 2001).

Indicators related to biomass or abundances and diversity varied significantly across LTEs and tillage practice. Mirroring the observed variation with the microfauna (nematodes) and to a certain extent with the microbial biomass, CREA (Italy) showed notably smaller biomass values than other sites (Figures 11 and 12). It is also relevant to highlight that INIA (Spain) reported no earthworms collected during the sampling. The absence of earthworms in Mediterranean sites can be attributed to several ecological and environmental factors, including unfavorable soil characteristics, such as high clay content and low organic matter, which limit their survival and reproduction. The hot, dry summers typical of Mediterranean climates create extended periods of low moisture availability, making it challenging for earthworms to thrive. Agricultural practices and land disturbances can disrupt soil structure and compaction, hindering earthworm movement and population density. Collectively, these factors can contribute to the limited occurrence of earthworms in Mediterranean agroecosystems, where alternative soil organisms (e.g. ants) may play more significant roles in nutrient cycling and soil structure.

Figure 11. Variation in earthworm biomass (g/m²) across LTEs and tillage treatment. Black diamond shows mean value per LTE. ST – Standard tillage, RT – Reduced tillage, NT – No Tillage. LTE acronyms as in Table 1.

The functional indicators used for macrofauna, specifically the proportional abundance of different ecological groups, varied across the long-term experiments (LTEs), reflecting the distinct functional composition of the earthworm community along the edaphoclimatic gradient. Endogeic species were the most abundant in all sites; however, CREA exhibited a significant proportional abundance of deep burrowing species at 30%. In contrast, in the other sites, the second most abundant group comprised epianecic species, which inhabit both surface and deeper soil layers. These functional indicators were mostly not sensitive to changes in management practices.

Figure 12. Variation in earthworm species richness across the studied LTEs. LTE acronyms as in Table 1.

4. Conclusions

This chapter reports just a few examples taken by the LTE experiments carried out in MINOTAUR and reported in detail in D4.2. Here, we provided an overview of the variation observed in several biological indicators related to the abundance, taxonomic diversity, and functional diversity of microbiota, as well as micro, meso-, and macrofauna across nine different long-term experiments (LTEs) located throughout the EU, all subjected to comparable tillage and fertilization treatments.

The results emphasize that the primary source of variation in soil health indicators, particularly those related to soil biodiversity and functioning, is attributed to the differences observed across the LTEs. This finding underscores the significance of geographical variations in soil conditions and climate, which in turn influence soil diversity and functioning. Furthermore, tillage practices (standard, reduced, and no tillage) emerged as the second most important factor driving variation within the LTEs. However, the effects of tillage were inconsistent across sites, indicating a complex interplay between soil management practices and local conditions that warrants further investigation. In contrast, there was considerably less variation associated with fertilization treatments (mineral, organic, and no fertilization), suggesting that their impact on soil biodiversity and functioning may be less significant compared to other factors.

These findings highlight the varying capacities of the studied indices to reflect changes in management practices and contribute to the establishment of locally adapted reference values based on edaphoclimatic conditions.

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